

AUTHENTIC PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL PRACTICES AMONG BEGINNING AND EXPERIENCED ENGLISH TEACHERS: AN EXPLANATORY SEQUENTIAL APPROACH

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Abstract. This study explored the significant difference in the authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers. In this study, the researcher selected 157 public secondary school teachers in District II in Davao City as the study's respondents in the quantitative phase. In comparison, 10 teachers were selected for IDI and FGD in the qualitative phase. A mixed-method research design using an explanatory sequential approach was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Percentage, and T-test for Independent Samples. Findings revealed that authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in District II, Davao City were rated as moderately extensive. T-test analysis proved that there is a significant difference in authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers. Thematic analysis indicated that the codes, diversity of assessment methods, alignment with learning objectives, authentic contexts, and cultural sensitivity confirmed the moderately extensive rating on authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers. Additionally, thematic analysis showed that the codes, student engagement and motivation, experience-based feedback, and innovative practices confirmed the significant difference in authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers. The study, therefore, was conducted for further utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journals.

KEY WORDS

1. Teaching English
2. authentic performance appraisal
3. practices of English
4. explanatory sequential approach

1. Introduction

Authentic performance appraisal practices evaluate students' abilities to apply language skills in real-world contexts. When appraisal practices are poor, they may fail to assess students' accurate proficiency levels accurately. This can lead to misinterpretations of student abilities and hinder the identification of areas needing improvement. Accordingly, inaccurate assessment practices impede students' language development by failing to provide the appropriate feedback and support they need to improve. This can result in stagnation or regression in students' language proficiency over time. Addressing the implications of poor authentic perfor-

mance appraisal practices requires a concerted effort to improve the validity, reliability, and fairness of assessment methods used in English language teaching. In a global setting, Brown et al. (2019) noted that when appraisal practices are poor, students may not receive the targeted feedback and support they need to improve their language skills effectively. This resulted in stagnation or regression in students' language proficiency levels over time, as they lacked opportunities to address their weaknesses and build upon their strengths. In the US education system, there is often a heavy reliance on standardized testing to measure student achievement and teacher effectiveness. Poor authentic performance appraisal practices may exacerbate the pressure to "teach to the test," prioritizing rote memorization and test-taking strategies over authentic language learning experiences (Kriewaldt et al., 2021). In Asia, Sultana (2019) noted that when appraisal practices prioritize standardized testing outcomes over authentic language learning experiences, there is a risk of narrowing the curriculum to focus solely on tested content. This can lead to a lack of emphasis on essential language skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and communication, essential for success in the 21st century. Taking things in the Philippine setting, Gepila (2020) asserted that when appraisal practices lack authenticity or relevance to students' learning experiences, students may become disengaged and demotivated. They perceive appraisal tasks as arbitrary or disconnected from their language learning goals, leading to decreased motivation and effort in language learning activities. According to Espino, Gonzales, and Martin (2021), authentic appraisal practices are aligned with

students' language learning goals and reflect real-world language use and tasks. However, when assessment tasks are perceived as arbitrary or disconnected from these goals, students may struggle to see the value in engaging with them. This disconnect can lead to a lack of motivation to invest in language learning activities. Most studies conducted on performance appraisal practices of English teachers in the Philippines, particularly in Davao City, have been either purely quantitative or purely qualitative. This has resulted in a limited understanding of the complex interplay between factors influencing appraisal practices, such as cultural context, teacher experiences, and student outcomes. In addition, no studies have been found in the literature on the perception of authentic assessment of both beginning and experienced English teachers. Thus, the current research would fill up the gap. This study was conducted in District II Davao City. This made use of a mixed method approach, specifically an explanatory sequential approach. For these reasons, it can be said that the research may contribute significant concepts to the related literature. A sequential explanatory mixed-method study would allow researchers to explore these factors more deeply and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. Also, by addressing the research gap through a mixed-method approach, researchers can generate findings that directly affect policy and practice. Insights from the study could inform the development of more effective appraisal systems, teacher training programs, and professional development initiatives tailored to the needs and contexts of English teachers in Davao City and beyond.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study addressed the significant difference in the perception of authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in Davao City. An explanatory sequential mixed methods design was used, and it involved collecting qualitative data after quantitative results to explain or follow up on the quantitative results in more depth. In the quantitative phase of the study, primary data was collected from the secondary

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

school teachers in District II, Davao City regarding their authentic performance appraisal practices. The qualitative phase was conducted to establish the authenticity of the model obtained from the quantitative results. The research questions underlying the investigation in this study are as follows:

- 1.2. *Research Questions*—Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:
- (1) What is the extent of authentic performance appraisal practices of English teachers?
 - (2) Is there a significant difference in authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers?
 - (3) What are the standpoints of the participants on the extent of authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers?
 - (4) What are the standpoints of the participants on the significant difference in the authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers?

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the researcher introduced the philosophical assumptions, qualitative assumptions, research participants, data collection, data analysis, ethical considerations, the role of the researcher, and trustworthiness. It is also worthy to note that in the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. *Research Design*—The researcher utilized a mixed methods approach in this study, specifically employing an explanatory sequential research design. As described by Toyon (2021), mixed methods research integrates qualitative and quantitative methodologies, encompassing the collection and analysis of both numerical data (such as measurements or statistical analyses) and qualitative data (such as observations or interviews). This comprehensive approach aims to achieve a deeper understanding of the research topic, particularly when investigating complex phenomena that cannot be fully elucidated using a singular methodologi-

cal approach. By combining diverse data collection and analysis techniques, researchers can leverage the strengths of each method while compensating for their respective limitations, thereby facilitating a more nuanced and comprehensive comprehension of the research problem. An explanatory sequential approach was a type of mixed methods approach where quantitative data was collected and analyzed first, followed by qualitative data collection and analysis to provide additional depth and understanding (Birgili Demir, 2022). In this design, the quantitative phase typically preceded the qualitative phase, and the qualitative phase was used to help explain or elaborate on the quantitative findings. This sequential process allowed researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem by integrating both quantitative and qualitative perspectives. By sequentially combining quantitative and qualitative data, researchers could gain deeper insights and provide a more comprehensive analysis of the research topic (Othman, Steen Fleet, 2020). In the quantitative phase, the researcher specifically used the descriptive-comparative research design was a methodology used to describe and compare different groups or variables to identify similarities, differences, or patterns. This approach involved collecting data on the variables of interest and then analyzing and comparing them to understand the relationships between them (Shahrokh Miri, 2019). In the context of determining the significant difference on the authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers, a descriptive-comparative research design was appropriate. This design allowed the researcher to describe the levels of authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers separately and then compare them to identify any significant differences. In the qualitative phase, the researcher used a phenomenological approach. A phenomenological study was a methodology used to explore and understand individuals' lived experiences, perceptions, and perspectives of a particular phenomenon. It focused on uncovering the essence or meaning of these experiences from the participants' own perspectives (Williams, 2021). Phenomenology focused on understanding individuals' lived experiences and the meanings they attributed to them. English teachers, especially those with varying levels of experience, brought rich and diverse experiences to their practice. Phenomenological research allowed for a deep exploration of these experiences, capturing nuances and subtleties that quantitative approaches may have overlooked. Phenomenology encouraged researchers to explore participants' subjective viewpoints and perspectives. This was particularly valuable in the context of performance appraisal practices, where individual experiences and perceptions could vary widely. By conducting in-depth interviews or focus groups, researchers gained insights into how beginning and experienced English teachers perceived and interpreted authentic appraisal practices. A sequential explanatory mixed method design was highly appropriate for understanding the experiences of English teachers, both beginning and experienced, regarding authentic performance appraisal practices. This design combined both qualitative and quantitative methods in a sequential manner, allowing researchers to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By starting with qualitative data collection and analysis, researchers could explore the rich and nuanced experiences of English teachers in depth. Subsequently, quantitative data collection and analysis could provide broader insights and corroborate qualitative findings, leading to a more complete understanding of the research topic. In the quantitative phase of the study, researchers had the opportunity to delve into relationships and associations between various variables associated with authentic performance appraisal practices and teachers'

experiences. This phase typically involved the collection and analysis of numerical data obtained through surveys, questionnaires, or other quantitative research instruments. The quantitative phase allowed researchers to quantify the relationship and association between variables, providing empirical evidence to support or refute hypotheses based on qualitative findings. By identifying statistically significant relationships, researchers could deepen their understanding of how specific aspects of performance appraisal practices impacted teachers' experiences. Lastly, the sequential explanatory mixed methods design facilitated data triangulation, whereby findings from different sources, such as qualitative and quantitative data, were compared and integrated to validate and enrich each other. Triangulation enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the study findings by corroborating qualitative insights with quantitative evidence and vice versa

2.2. Research Respondents—In the quantitative phase, the researcher selected 155 secondary school teachers in District II, Davao City. The respondents were selected using a stratified random sampling technique. According to Riaz et al. (2022), stratified random sampling is a sampling technique where the population is divided into subgroups, or strata, based on specific characteristics relevant to the research. Random samples are then independently selected from each stratum. This method ensures that each subgroup is represented proportionally in the sample, leading to a more representative and accurate sample overall. In selecting secondary school teachers, where the three schools were the strata, implementing stratified random sampling would involve several steps. The first step was to identify the strata, which were the three secondary schools in District II, Davao City. Once the strata are identified, the population of secondary school teachers is divided into three groups, each corresponding to one of the selected schools. The next step was to determine

the sample size for each stratum. This can be done proportionally based on the size of the teacher population in each school or using a predetermined ratio. Within each school, a random sample of teachers was selected. This can be done using various randomization techniques, such as random number generators or random selection from a list of teachers. Once the samples are selected from each stratum, they are combined to form the study's final sample of secondary school teachers. The researcher implemented inclusion criteria when selecting the respondents. The inclusion criteria were current English language teachers and teachers willing to participate in the study. This diversity enhanced the validity and generalizability of the study findings, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of how these practices impacted English language teachers in different contexts. Additionally, ensuring voluntary participation and obtaining informed consent upheld ethical standards in research conduct and protected the rights and privacy of the respondents. In the qualitative phase, the researcher purposively selected 5 secondary school teachers for the in-depth interview (IDI) and 5 secondary school teachers for the focus group discussion (FGD). A total of 10 secondary school teachers in District II, Davao City were invited as participants. Purposive sampling was utilized in selecting the participants of the study. Purposive sampling is a non-random sampling technique where researchers deliberately choose participants who possess specific characteristics or meet predetermined criteria relevant to the research objectives. Purposive sampling allowed researchers to target individuals most likely to provide rich and relevant information pertinent to the study objectives, thereby enhancing the depth and quality of the research findings.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used two sets of instruments: one for the quantitative phase and one for the qualitative phase. A panel of experts subjected these questionnaires

to content validity and underwent pilot testing to test their validity and reliability. The experts' comments, corrections, and suggestions were incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires.

Range of Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The authentic performance appraisal practices is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The authentic performance appraisal practices is oftentimes observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The authentic performance appraisal practices is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The authentic performance appraisal practices is rarely observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The authentic performance appraisal practices is never observed.

In the quantitative phase, the study employed questionnaires adapted from different studies and was modified to fit the context of the respondents of this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument concerned the teachers' authentic performance appraisal practices, which was adopted from the study of Metin (2011), indicating the attitude towards using performance assessment in the classroom, attitude towards authentic assessment, and attitude towards self and peer assessment. The reliability of the original scale was 0.912, which made it reliable. Using a semi-structured interview, the researcher conducted an IDI and

FGD with 10 public secondary English teachers. The researcher-made semi-structured interview guide comprised general questions with probing questions to elaborate and dig deeper into the participants' thoughts. This interview guide was developed upon consultation, reviewed by the experts, and underwent several processes to accommodate their suggestions. The components to be validated include the language and the conceptual levels of questions if suited to the participant's level of understanding, the suitability of the items to the research design in which there should be no leading questions, and the alignment of the interview questions to the objective of the study.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance certificate from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC). The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance certificate from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee

(RMC-REC) was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public secondary schools in District II, Davao City. The researcher identified and recruited 155 public secondary school English teachers from District II, Davao City. Before data collection, the researchers obtained informed consent from all respondents, explaining the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Respondents were allowed

to ask questions and clarify any concerns before agreeing to participate in the study. The researcher explained that the survey questionnaires measure their perceptions of authentic performance appraisal practices. In the quantitative phase, survey questionnaires were distributed to secondary school English teachers from District II, Davao City. The data collected through these questionnaires served as the basis for analyzing the authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced teachers. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, each respondent's scores were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After this, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. Data were analyzed using statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics and inferential statistics to examine differences between groups and the overall distribution of responses. In the qualitative phase, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with secondary school English teachers to gather rich and detailed information about their perception of authentic performance appraisal practices. The interviews were conducted in a private and comfortable setting, such as the participant's homes or schools, to ensure confidentiality and encourage open communication. The researcher used open-ended questions and prompts to elicit detailed responses from the teachers, allowing them to share their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in their own words. During the interviews, the researcher took detailed notes and recorded audio or video with the participants' consent. This allowed for a comprehensive record of the interviews, capturing the nuances of the student's responses and providing rich data for analysis. Lastly, the researcher synthesized quantitative and qualitative findings, weaving together both data sets to develop a comprehensive narrative addressing the research objectives. They interpreted the findings in light of existing literature and theoretical frameworks, drawing meaningful conclusions

about authentic performance appraisal practices for beginning and experienced secondary English teachers.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Quantitative Phase.

The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data: Mean. This was useful in characterizing the authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in District II, Davao City. T-Test for Independent Samples. It was used in this study to assess the significant difference on authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers in District II, Davao City. Qualitative Phase. The researcher conducted qualitative interviews or focus group discussions with beginning and experienced teachers to gather rich, in-depth data on their experiences and perspectives on authentic performance appraisal practices. Students were encouraged to share their thoughts, feelings, and experiences openly and honestly during these interviews or discussions. After the interviews or focus group discussions, the researcher transcribed the audio recordings or notes taken during the sessions. This ensured that the data were accurately captured and preserved for analysis. After the transcription, the researchers familiarized themselves with the data by reading and re-reading the transcripts multiple times. This process helped the researcher comprehensively understand the content and identify initial ideas or patterns within the dataset. The researcher systematically coded the data by identifying meaningful information units or "codes" that captured key concepts, ideas, or themes related to adolescent reproductive health literacy. This involved highlighting relevant text passages and assigning descriptive labels or codes to them. The researcher organized the coded data into broader themes or patterns that emerged from the dataset. Themes represented recurrent topics, ideas, or experiences shared by the participants and captured the main findings of the

study. The researcher reviewed the coded data and developed themes, ensuring that they accurately reflected the content of the dataset and captured the diversity of participants' perspectives. Themes were refined through iterative analysis and discussion among researchers to enhance their clarity and coherence. Finally, the researcher interpreted the themes in relation to the research questions and objectives, considering how they shed light on the experiences and perceptions of beginning and experienced English teachers regarding authentic performance appraisal practices. Interpretation involved synthesizing the findings, identifying implications for theory and practice, and considering any limitations or biases in the data.

Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures. In the sequence, the researcher determined a logical sequence for data collection activities, considering factors such as research objectives, study design, and ethical considerations. Sequential data collection methods may have been employed, with quantitative data collection preceding qualitative data collection or vice versa, depending on the research design. For instance, the researcher have first administered surveys or questionnaires to gather quantitative data on their perception related to authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers. Subsequently, qualitative data collection methods such as interviews or focus group discussions have been conducted to explore participants' experiences, perceptions, and attitudes in greater depth. In the emphasis stage, the researcher may have emphasized certain aspects of data collection based on the research objectives and the level of importance assigned to different variables or themes. For instance, the researcher may have emphasized data collection related to gender identity and its influence on knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors. Lastly, the mixing procedures involve integrating quantitative and qualitative data collection methods to enhance the overall data collection process and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic. The researcher has used a mixed methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative data collection techniques to triangulate findings and corroborate results. The quantitative surveys or questionnaires may have been supplemented with qualitative interviews or focus group discussions to capture the richness and complexity of participants' experiences and perspectives.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the researcher reflects the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings. Specifically, this chapter reveals quantitative and qualitative data relevant to the research questions formulated in Chapter 1. The tabulated quantitative findings were presented in Tables 1-2, while qualitative findings were presented in Figures 3-4.

Results on Table 1 show the overall extent of authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in District II in Davao City. The table shows that authentic performance appraisal practices of novice and seasoned teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.29, which is moderately extensive.

This indicates that there are instances where

teachers prioritize practical and meaningful tasks that are part of their everyday instructional duties. The outcome aligns with Wahyuni's (2019) perspective, which suggests that authentic performance evaluations enable language instructors to be assessed based on their capacity to implement teaching theories and methods in genuine classroom contexts. This encompasses their utilization of language teaching strategies,

Fig. 2. Flow of Procedures

Table 1. Authentic Performance Appraisal Practices of Beginning and Experienced English Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Attitude towards Using Performance Assessment in Classroom	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Attitude towards Performance Assessment	3.46	Extensive
Attitudes towards Self and Peer Assessment	3.05	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.29	Moderately Extensive

management of classroom dynamics, and involvement of students in substantive language learning endeavors. Moreover, authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in terms of Attitude towards Using Performance Assessment in Classroom acquired a mean score of 3.37 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. This indicates that at times, teachers' attitudes toward integrating assessment methods that measure students' genuine performance are apparent. This is consistent with the perspective of Evalinda et al. (2020), who suggest that performance assessment is in line with the principles of authentic language learning and assessment, emphasizing real-world language usage and activities. By evaluating students' capacity to apply language skills in authentic settings, teachers can offer more substantial feedback and effectively facilitate their language development. On one hand, authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in terms of Attitude towards Performance Assessment acquired a mean score of 3.46 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed. This shows that teachers' viewpoints, convictions, and emotions regarding the utilization of assessment methods that gauge students'

authentic language skills and capabilities are oftentimes observed. This reinforces the assertion made by Soodmand Afshar and Hosseini Yar (2019) that performance assessment allows educators to evaluate different language abilities, such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing, in a comprehensive manner. By assessing students' competencies across various language domains, teachers acquire a more thorough grasp of their language proficiency levels. On the other hand, authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in terms of Attitudes towards Self and Peer Assessment yielded a mean score of 3.05 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. This suggests that teachers' viewpoints, convictions, and emotions regarding the inclusion of self-assessment and peer assessment methods in evaluating students' language skills and abilities are sometimes observed. This aligns with the concept proposed by Huertas Abril et al. (2021) that involvement in self and peer assessment tasks prompts students to reflect on their language performance, recognize strengths and weaknesses, and cultivate metacognitive skills. This heightened metacognitive awareness improves students' capacity to effectively monitor and control their language learning processes.

Table 2 presents the percentage frequency distribution on authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced teachers in North District, Davao del Sur. It reveals that there are 18 teachers or 11.61 percent belongs to less extensive ratings, there are 68 or 43.87 percent acquired moderately extensive rating, there are 69 or 44.52 percent gained extensive rating, and there are 2 or 1.29 percent gained extensive rating on authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in District II, Davao City. This shows that most of the experienced teachers are more effective in using authentic performance appraisal compared to beginning teachers. Moreover, the table indicates the significant difference on the authentic performance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers in District II, Davao City was computed using t-test for Independent Samples. It was revealed on the table that there is a significant difference on the authentic per-

formance appraisal practices between beginning and experienced English teachers. The results of the analysis revealed that the mean scores on the authentic performance appraisal practices of experienced English teachers do significantly differ with the authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning English teachers. Comparative analysis revealed that the difference of 0.12 is statistically different (Difference = 0.2827, $t = 0.440$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and concluded that there is an empirical evidence to determine that authentic performance appraisal practices of experienced English teachers differ from the beginning English teachers. This suggests that due to their familiarity with the appraisal procedures, experienced teachers tend to navigate the process more efficiently. They possess a clear understanding of the expectations, know how to compile the required documentation effectively, and are adept at engaging constructively with the feedback provided. This aligns with Myyry

Fig. 3. Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Authentic Performance Appraisal Practices of Beginning and Experienced English Teachers

et al.’s (2022) assertion that veteran educators typically have a greater grasp of the appraisal procedures, potentially leading to increased efficiency. They possess a clear comprehension of the requirements, adeptly organize the essential documentation, and effectively respond to feedback in a constructive manner

3.1. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Quantitative Results Regarding the Authentic Performance Appraisal Practices of Beginning and Experienced English Teachers—*

3.1.1. *Diversity of Assessment Methods—*Embracing a diverse range of assessment methods enables teachers to gain a more holistic understanding of students’ learning. Rather than relying solely on standardized tests, teachers can use varied assessment approaches to capture different aspects of student performance, including critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills.

3.1.2. *Alignment with Learning Objectives—*The moderate level of authentic performance appraisal practices among teachers can

3.2. *Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Difference on Authentic Performance Appraisal Practices of Beginning and Experienced English Teachers—*

largely be attributed to challenges in aligning assessments with learning objectives. Factors such as limited training, time constraints, resource limitations, and the need to balance multiple objectives all contribute to this issue.

3.1.3. *Authentic Contexts—*The moderate level of authentic performance appraisal practices among teachers can be attributed to challenges in fully integrating authentic contexts into assessments. Factors such as resource limitations, the need for professional development, balancing practicality with authenticity, and curriculum constraints all contribute to this moderate level of practice.

3.1.4. *Cultural Sensitivity—*The moderate level of authentic performance appraisal practices among teachers can be attributed to challenges in fully integrating cultural sensitivity into assessments. Factors such as inconsistent application, limited training, resource constraints, diverse student needs, and lack of institutional support all contribute to this moderate level of practice.

3.2.1. *Student Engagement and Motivation—*Authentic performance appraisal recognizes experienced teachers’ ability to tailor instruction to meet the diverse needs and interests of students. These teachers have honed their

Fig. 4. Standpoints of the Participants on the Significant Difference on Authentic Performance Appraisal Practices Between Beginning and Experienced English Teachers

skills to design lessons that are engaging, relevant, and meaningful, capturing students’ attention and fostering active participation.

3.2.2. *Experience-Based Feedback*—Experienced English teachers have spent years honing their craft in the classroom, which gives them a wealth of firsthand experience to draw upon when providing feedback. This experience allows them to offer nuanced insights into teaching practices, student engagement, and learning outcomes. By drawing upon their wealth of classroom experience, contextual understanding, and reflective practice, these teachers play a crucial role in improving student learning outcomes and fostering a culture of continuous improvement in English education.

3.2.3. *Innovative Practices*—Emphasizing innovative practices in the performance ap-

praisal of both beginning and experienced English teachers is essential for promoting student engagement, lifelong learning, and the continuous evolution of teaching methods. By integrating creative and forward-thinking approaches into the evaluation process, educators can be encouraged to adopt new strategies that cater to diverse learning styles, thus making lessons more engaging and effective. Furthermore, such practices foster an environment where teachers are motivated to pursue ongoing professional development, enhancing their skills and knowledge. This commitment to continuous improvement benefits individual teachers and contributes to the advancement of educational practices, ensuring that the teaching methods remain dynamic and responsive to the evolving needs of students.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the researcher’s conclusion and recommendation. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion is by statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. *Findings*—This study aimed to determine the significant difference in the authentic performance appraisal practices by beginning and experienced English teachers in Dis-

trict II in Davao City using mixed methods, specifically the sequential-explanatory design wherein adapted survey questionnaires will be used in the quantitative phase and through in-

depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD) in the qualitative phase. On the one hand, in the quantitative phase of the study, adapted survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the English teachers to determine the extent of authentic performance appraisal practices employed by the beginning and experienced English teachers. For the quantitative strand, the researcher used modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument, while a semi-structured interview guide was used in the qualitative strand. Based on the results, the summary of the findings were following: Authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in District II in Davao City were moderately extensive. Meanwhile, authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in terms of attitude towards using performance assessment in the classroom and attitudes towards self and peer were rated as moderately extensive, while authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in terms of attitude towards performance assessment was rated as extensive. The authentic performance appraisal practices of experienced English teachers in District II in Davao City significantly differ from those of beginning English teachers. The quantitative results were further substantiated by codes that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. On the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the moderately extensive rating on authentic performance appraisal practices by beginning and experienced English teachers, the four emerging codes are as follows: Diversity of assessment methods, alignment with learning objectives, authentic contexts, and cultural sensitivity. From

the standpoints of the participants on the quantitative results regarding the significant difference in authentic performance appraisal practices between the beginning and experienced English teachers, the three emerging codes are as follows: Student engagement and motivation, experience-based feedback, and innovative practices.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions such as the survey questionnaire and number of respondents, several conclusions are generated: Authentic performance appraisal practices of beginning and experienced English teachers in District II in Davao City were moderately extensive and interpreted as often observed. This indicates that there are instances where teachers prioritize practical and meaningful tasks that are part of their everyday instructional duties. The outcome aligns with Wahyuni's (2019) perspective, which suggests that authentic performance evaluations enable language instructors to be assessed based on their capacity to implement teaching theories and methods in genuine classroom contexts. The authentic performance appraisal practices of experienced English teachers significantly differ from those of beginning English teachers in District II in Davao City. This suggests that teachers sometimes prioritize practical and meaningful tasks that were integral to their daily teaching responsibilities. This result is consistent with the viewpoint expressed by Wahyuni (2019), who proposes that authentic performance assessments allow language educators to be evaluated according to their ability to apply teaching theories and methods in real classroom situations. Codes that emerged during the thematic analysis of the qualitative data further substantiated the quantitative results, generally confirming the results of the quantitative aspects of the study. The salient quantitative and qualitative findings revealed a parallel result. The corroborated finding means

that the quantitative and qualitative findings merged and connected.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education should allocate resources and funding for ongoing professional development programs for English teachers. These programs should focus on enhancing their knowledge and skills related to authentic performance appraisal practices. DepEd should develop policy frameworks that encourage the integration of authentic assessment into English language curricula. Ensure that evaluations align with 21st-century skills and cultural sensitivity. School principals may provide regular feedback to teachers on their assessment practices and support improvement. They may acknowledge and celebrate innovative and effective approaches. In addition, they may foster a school culture that encourages collaboration among teachers. Peer-to-peer sharing of assessment strategies can be

highly beneficial. English teachers may proactively seek professional development opportunities to enhance their assessment skills. They may stay updated on the latest trends and best practices in authentic assessment. They may also collaborate with fellow English teachers to share insights and learn from one another's experiences. Peer collaboration can lead to the discovery of effective assessment strategies. Future researchers and individuals in academic may explore cross-cultural differences in authentic assessment practices and their impact on learning outcomes. This can provide valuable insights into cultural sensitivity in assessment. They should continue to build a body of research that identifies and shares best practices in authentic assessment and collaborate with educators to bridge the gap between research and practice.

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